

Sociolinguistic Profile Research Paper

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Abstract: This research paper presents an in-depth sociolinguistic analysis of a cohort of 9th grade students, aged 14-15, engaged in English language learning for general purposes at a centrally located school. Also, paper highlights the importance of instruction to the specific needs and aims of the students and every teacher should consider learners' cultural background, linguistic experience, and learning styles when designing lessons. Through examining students' linguistic identities, language attitudes, and communicative practices, this study seeks to elucidate how language usage and adaptation are shaped by the social and cultural dynamics within this demographic. Key pedagogical implications are discussed, emphasizing tailored teaching strategies that address the needs of both subgroups and promote an inclusive classroom environment.

Keywords: culture, gender, ethnicity, identity, pedagogical implications, language attitudes, assessment, sociocultural diversity, religion, communicative practices, instruction.

Introduction

The research paper gives information about school learners with age between 14-15 and delves into the sociolinguistic profile of 9th grade students, aiming to crystalize on how language is used and adapted within this particular demographic group. They are learning the English language for general purposes in one of the local schools of the city, which is located in the city center. The class are divided into two sub groups: L1 users of Russian and L1 users of Uzbek. Also, this study uncovers the unique linguistic identities, language attitudes and communicative practices that learners bring to the classroom.

Sociolinguistic Profile of a Group of Learners

My target learners are school adolescents, and they have been learning English as a foreign language since primary school. There are 16 students in group, and their age are 14-15. They are 9th grade students and according to the CEFR their level is B1. They are studying in one of the local school in our city. The learners come from different villages and have different learning styles and motivation. Their background language not bad, they are eager to learn English for different purposes. They know grammar rules, which helps them to make sentences in the correct way. Moreover, with the knowledge of vocabulary they can understand reading and listening texts. This group is Russian so students' literacy started in the Russian language. They study all subjects in this language. They mostly taught by GTM and TPR methods. Some common issues in my class are sometimes learners have difficulty in speaking, they do not have an ability to express themselves clearly. Also, their pronunciation not very well with fluency. No one speaks the same way all time, and every individual constantly exploit variation within languages they speak for a wide variety of purposes (Wardhough et al., 2014, p. 6).

Subgroup 1 L1 users of Russian

These subgroup learners are sociable and they are Russian so they do not speak in the Uzbek language very well. Majority of them was born in Moscow and they moved to our country as a reason of their parents' job and others was born in the city. These subgroups' learners are from upper-class and they have an opportunity and variety resources to improve their knowledge. Also, they are very confident even if they make some mistakes during speech. They learned the language with instrumental motivation, because the majority of their friends can communicate in the English language. They are an auditory learner who benefits from listening to podcasts and music in English, because they always prefer this kind of method. Moreover, they interested in listening so they are always with their headphones. Moreover, some of them come across with native speakers, because with family they go around in every holidays. Labov (1963) stated that "Social pressures are continually operating upon language, not from some remote point in the past, but as an immanent social force acting in the living present" (p. 275). Their fluency is better than accuracy and during the lesson they are very active and speak without hesitations but make some grammar mistakes.

Subgroup 2 L1 users of Uzbek

The learners of this subgroup are Uzbek and they are from different villages. They are not fluent, because their Russian, Uzbek and dialects affected on the phonology of English. Kim and Richardson (2018) emphasizes that increasing multilingual practices and linguistic diversity has challenged the conventional view of language and communicative competence.

They are from mixed class such as middle and working class. Mather found in 2012 that "non-standard dialects were not simply ungrammatical but had their own set of rules" (p. 52). They mostly do self-studies and they want to improve their communication skill. Some of this learners are very shy but very intelligent and they have an extrinsic motivation to learn the language. They are good learner who excels in reading and writing but in listening and speaking they have difficulties. The girls from this subgroup mostly prefer to be silent, because their family religious and they do not show themselves in the lessons.

From Subgroup 1: Mixail

He is Russian and he is 15 years old. He is sociable and confident boy. He is from rich family; his parents are well-known businessman in the city. Mixail is from Tashkent and he lives in the city center. He has a lot of opportunities to improve his language skill because parents always support him with the latest technology to learn foreign language. He uses only the Russian language in the communication. He loves showing off himself and always want to be dominant in the class with creating only Russian atmosphere by ignoring the Uzbek language. He can speak with non-stop, he prefers to learn with communication. He values teamwork and leadership skill developed through sports participation.

From subgroup 2: Laziza

Laziza very shy and she is 14 years old. Laziza is a good learner who is bilingual in English and Uzbek. She is from one of the villages of Samarqand. She does not have more opportunity to access to educational alternatives at home due to she is from working-class family. During the communication her dialect influences to the speech so she prefers to be silent. Other students from city do not want to listen her speech and they require to speak more in Russian.

Sociolinguistic Profile of the Learning Context

The environment of the classroom plays vital role in acquiring the language. The classroom is a standard public school with mixed abilities for general purpose. The location of the school in the city. School are not modern and the number of the modern tools are limited such as whiteboard and computers. Not all classes are equipped with the computer or speakers to do the listening tasks. Teachers are well qualified, some teachers are monolingual and they had a training

sections. As Kim and Richardson highlighted in 2018 that teachers must have the sort of the training and experiences that can reorient them toward adopting concepts of linguistic diversity and teaching practices relevant to the effective instruction (p. 2). In terms of the gender and racial composition of these classes, it is vital to create a diverse and inclusive learning atmosphere where all students feel represented and valued. In addition, in class students are from different nations such as Uzbek, Russian and some students are from villages and their dialects are different. Russian students use only the Russian Language in their communication with each other. Sometimes they want to ignore students from other villages due to their dialect. Russian and students from city try to be dominant and leader of the class and they do not let speak or use students' dialect in the class. In addition, Russian students always want to create Russian environment without the Uzbek language. If someone would use their Uzbek, they ignore it and say to use the Russian language and you are studying in the Russian group. Moreover, they will tell these gaps to the teachers, who use their native language. As Baugh (2005) stated that "racial differences and controversies over affirmative action have tended to divide us, the recognition that most of our ancestors came from lands where English was foreign gives us a common historical bond" (p. 163). Their character's also are different as an example Russian students are comfortable with their speech and always give their own idea, while Uzbek students from different villages prefer silent way and they afraid to hurt others' feelings. During the lesson, teacher should be mindful of any potential gender or racial biases in their teaching practices and materials, and ensure that all learners have equal opportunities to participate and succeed in the classroom. Moreover, incorporating culturally relevant materials or contents and debates can help learners from different backgrounds feel more comfortable engaged and connected to the material. Topics which are related to the sex and gender should not be discussed in the class because some learners come from religious class. "Adolescents are viewed as emotional, changeable, irrational and unobjective" (Eckert, 2003, p.382). Also, the materials should be chosen properly with pictures, which can be appropriate to use everyone. Addressing fluency and pronunciation for everyone will be important for them. Schilling (2011) stated that for stable sociolinguistic variables, female show a lower rate of stigmatized variants and a higher rate of prestige variants than men (p.234). As an example, female use higher levels of the standard pronunciation of the -ing suffix (as in swimming) and male use higher level of nonstandard -in (as in swimming).

Sociolinguistic Profile of the Context where English will be Used

Learners are learning the English language for different purposes and majority of them want to get a certificate such as IELTS and CEFR. With this kind of certificates, they can enter the top universities of the city or they can go study abroad with their IELTS. Some of them want to work in the English atmosphere so they try hard to learn the language effectively. They want to improve their communication skill because some of them want to be an interpreter. If their major subjects are different these students learn English because of their interest. They know that modern technologies always require knowing the foreign language. Phillipson (1992) argues that English has a dominant position in the variety things such as in science, technology, medicine, computers, in diplomacy and international organizations (p. 6).

Pedagogical Implications Methods and Approaches

Booven (2018) stated that by raising learners' conscious awareness of key sociolinguistic concepts, teachers can help their students to both recognize and produce systematic variation of language forms according to their varying appropriateness across different contexts and conditions of use (p. 4).

For the first subgroup it will be beneficial to focus on communicative language teaching methods because it is vital to capitalize on their sociable nature and confidence. This approach emphasizes real-life communication and interaction in the target language. To boost their skills, methods such as Audio-lingual teaching, Task-Based learning and Total Physical Response will be used. Incorporating activities that cater to their auditory learning preferences, such as listening

to podcasts or videos, music in English, can further enhance their language ability. With this kind of implications their interest will be supported and lead to improve their skills.

For second subgroup, providing opportunities for them to practice speaking in a supportive and encouraging environment, such as small group debates or pair-work activities, can boost their communication skill. Considering the character, creating a safe and inclusive learning classroom where girls feel comfortable expressing themselves is key. Encouraging these students to participate actively in variety activities that helps to build confidence, such as role plays or presentations, can help them overcome shyness and engage more actively in the activities in the classroom. Additionally, incorporating cultural elements and making connections to their background can help engage in the language learning process.

Material

As Kim and Richard (2018) argued that schools provide different language support programs for those who learn English as a foreign language (p. 2). For first subgroup, authentic material will help to boost skills. Using real-life materials such as newspapers, videos and audio-recordings to expose to authentic language use. Moreover, selection of books that are appropriate for their level and including a mix of grammar explanations, vocabulary exercises will help to have an improvement.

For second group, providing visual materials like flashcards, presentations, charts and pictures to aid vocabulary retention will boost their knowledge. Online resources that offer interactive activities can help improve listening skills while making the learning process more engaging. Addressing phonological challenges through targeted listening and speaking activities is vital.

Classroom practices

In terms of classroom activities, it would be helpful to create a supportive, warm and inclusive environment where both students feel comfortable expressing themselves without hesitation. Also, incorporating a different teaching methods and interactive activities can cater to the variety learning styles of students. Providing feedback and encouragement will motivate them to continue boosting their language skills. Using clear explanations, in-class corrections, and short grammar quizzes will be beneficial for them.

For second learners, addressing pronunciation issues empathetically. To confidence-building activities, it will be important to start with pair or small group discussions on familiar topics to build confidence.

Overall, it is vital to tailor teaching methods and approaches to meet the specific needs of each subgroup, taking into account their sociocultural background, learning preferences and language challenges. By understanding students' individual strengths and challenges, the teacher can create a supportive learning style that caters to their needs." Proficiency in a language is understood as a matter of individual competence" (Kim et al., 2018, p.2).

Assessment Implications

As their background is different I will try to avoid using questions which is related to the socio-economy and I will try to keep balance between students and encourage work with each other. Some girls are from religious family and they sometimes do not want to work with the male peers, so I will divide them into groups with female. Consequently, they will feel comfort and without hesitation they can focus to the given task. Besides this, I will support my learners in the class. For example, before doing the task we will do brainstorming activities and will answer the questions they have. As the majority of students are interested in the communication skill I try to do more speaking activities to boost their comprehension and improve their fluency. My learners are young so they prefer to work with the latest technology so I will use different games such as online quizzes, tests and presentations. After each assessment I will provide feedback to

everyone, which helps them work on their mistakes or errors. As Anne (2018) noted that it is critical not to focus grammatical errors in students; speech, oral reading, and writing to the point that the quality of the context, organization, or style of the student's work is overlooked. To correct their pronunciation, I will show them video TEDs talks and parts of the movies or cartoons. During the lesson we have some shy students and they may have difficulty to express themselves so to handle this situation I will use different and interesting written activities.

Conclusion

This portfolio about language instructor plays a vital role in advocating for specific learners with the context. By understanding and valuing the diverse backgrounds, languages, and experiences of the students' teachers can create inclusive, warm and supportive learning atmosphere that cater to individual needs. However, in advocating for specific learners, language instructions can support linguistic diversity, promote cultural understanding, and provide support to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to succeed. Instructor by recognizing the strengths and challenges of each learner with their sociolinguistic context can empower students to accept their identities and develop their language skills. Deumert (2011) noted that language play an important role in the enactment of multicultural policies as it is often central to the identity of different groups within a nation (p. 281). Learning the language can be for different reasons in these way the teacher' role help them learn the language effectively with understanding specific linguistic context. Also, it is crucial to understand the unique needs and difficulties that each student faces in their language learning process and to provide them with appropriate support and resources.

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